

Synthesis based on Cyclohexadienes. Part-27¹. Synthesis of Functionalized Tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecanes^Ψ

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A new methodology for the construction of tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecanes is described from indane-4-carboxylic acids. Birch reduction of indane-4-carboxylic acids followed by conjugation and cycloaddition with α -chloroacrylonitrile and hydrolysis lead to the tricyclic compounds 36 and 48 which are intermediates in the eremolactone synthesis.

There are very few natural products which contain the novel tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecane 1 ring system. These include the biogenetically novel diterpene, eremolactone 2², its acid catalyzed rearrangement product, isoeremolactone 3³, the sesquiterpenes, *allo*-cedrol 4⁴, its antipode, khusiol⁵ and α -duprezianene 5⁶. Although total syntheses of 2⁷, 3⁸ and 4⁹ have been accomplished, the construction of this novel tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecane skeleton continues to be a challenging task to organic chemists despite many reports¹⁰⁻¹². We now describe a new strategy for the construction of some functionalized tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecanes as possible intermediates for the total synthesis of eremolactone and isoeremolactone.

A closer examination of 1 indicates that it contains a bicyclo[2.2.2]octane subunit. We have earlier reported¹³ a facile method for the construction of functionalized bicyclo[2.2.2]octenes having a bridgehead methyl group by the Diels-Alder reaction of 2-carboxy- and 3-carboxy-1-methylcyclohexa-1,3-dienes with dienophiles wherein the methyl group directed the cycloaddition to form regio-specific adducts as exemplified, 6→7. This methodology has been used¹⁴ in the total synthesis of (\pm)-seychellene. Extension

Scheme 1

Scheme 2. Reagents : (a) Na, liq.NH₃, quant, (b) CH₂N₂, ether, quant, (c) for R=H : 20% aq.NaOH reflux, 88%; for R = Me : DBU, PhH, 97%, (d) H₂C=CHCO₂Me, Δ , 73%, (e) Pd-C/H₂, MeOH, quant.

tion of this strategy with an appropriate diene of the type 12 would furnish the adducts 13 and 14 which, on Dieckmann

^ΨDedicated to Prof. T. R. Govindachari on his 80th birthday.

cyclization, should result in the tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecane derivatives having the required functionality for elaboration into isoeremolactone as indicated in the retrosynthetic protocol (Scheme 1). The tricyclic aldehyde **27** is chosen as the initial target, starting from the known¹⁵ 3-(2-carboxyphenyl)propanoic acid **8** since this has been converted⁸ into isoeremolactone **3**.

Birch reduction of 3-(2-carboxyphenyl)propanoic acid **8** furnished the dihydro acid **9** (Scheme 2) characterized as its dimethyl ester **10** having the ir absorption at 1735 cm⁻¹. The ¹H nmr spectrum of **10** showed resonances due to the three olefinic protons as multiplets at δ 5.4–5.78 besides the methoxyl and methylene protons. Refluxing the acid **9** with 20% aqueous NaOH solution yielded the conjugated diacid **11** which showed the presence of two olefinic protons in its ¹H nmr spectrum at δ 5.71 and 6.28 as a broad doublet and a multiplet due to the C₃ and C₄ protons respectively, in addition to the methylene protons. Reaction of the diester **10** with DBU in refluxing benzene afforded the conjugated diester **12**, identical with the product obtained by the esterification of the diacid **11** with ethereal diazomethane.

Cycloaddition of the conjugated acid **11** with methyl acrylate followed by esterification of the resulting product with ethereal diazomethane afforded the regioisomeric triesters **13** and **14** in a 1 : 2 ratio. These were easily separated by column chromatography on silica gel and characterized. The ¹H nmr spectrum of **14** indicated the presence of an olefinic proton at δ 7.2 as a doublet, three singlets due to three carbomethoxyl groups at δ 3.53, 3.56 and 3.6, and a doublet at δ 2.53 due to the methine proton adjacent to the carbomethoxyl group besides the methylene protons, while that of the adduct **13** showed the olefinic proton at δ 7.02 as a doublet, carbomethoxyl groups as singlets at δ 3.5, 3.54 and 3.62, and the methine proton adjacent to the carbomethoxyl group at δ 2.56–2.66 as a multiplet. Further confirmation of the structures of the adducts **13** and **14** was obtained from the hydrogenation experiments. Catalytic hydrogenation of **14** afforded the triester **16** having a planar symmetry as observed from its ¹³C nmr signals which showed 12 lines for the 16 carbon atoms. However, hydrogenation of **13** yielded the product **15** whose ¹³C nmr spectrum indicated 16 lines for the 16 carbon atoms as expected¹³. The same mixture of regioisomeric adducts was obtained when the conjugated diester **12** was used as the diene in the Diels-Alder reaction.

The next task in the synthesis was to construct the tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecane system from the bicyclo[2.2.2]octane moiety. It was anticipated that Dieckmann cyclization of **14** would produce the tricyclic compound **21** (Scheme 3) on the assumption¹⁶ that the α,β -unsaturated ester would not participate in the cyclization due to its decreased carbonyl character. Decarboxylation of **21** should yield the tricyclic

ketone **22**.

Dieckmann cyclization of the triester **14** with sodium hydride afforded a product which showed ir absorptions at 1735 and 1650 cm⁻¹ due to the saturated ester and a β -ketoester functionalities. The ¹H nmr spectrum showed the presence of a doublet of a doublet at δ 2.56 for the methine proton adjacent to the carbomethoxyl group, two singlets at 3.6 and 3.77 for the two carbomethoxyl protons and a doublet at 6.64 due to the olefinic proton besides the methylene and methine protons appearing as multiplets in the range 0.8–3.24. The structure of the Dieckmann cyclization product of **14** was assumed to be **19** and not the required β -ketoester **21** from the above data since the product had the saturated ester group. Further, the vinylic proton shifted upfield in the product (δ 6.64) as compared to the starting material (δ 7.2) which is significant indicating that the cyclization had taken place with the unsaturated ester. This observation was further substantiated by the fact that Dieckmann cyclization of the isomeric triester **13** afforded a β -ketoester **17** whose ¹H nmr spectrum showed the presence of the olefinic proton at δ 6.56 as a doublet.

Scheme 3 Reagents . (a) NaH, PhH, Δ , (b) NaCl, DMSO, Δ

Decarboxylation of the β -ketoester **19** under Krapcho's condition¹⁷ afforded the ketoester **20** which showed the presence of a saturated ester (1734 cm⁻¹) and an α,β -unsaturated ketone (1716 cm⁻¹) in its ir spectrum. The ¹H nmr spectrum of **20** showed a triplet at δ 2.44 due to methylene protons adjacent to the ketone, a doublet of a doublet at 2.78 for the C-9 methine proton and a doublet at 7.18 for the olefinic proton besides the methoxyl and methylenic protons. Similar decarboxylation of the β -ketoester **17** furnished the unsaturated ketoester **18** which showed a doublet at δ 7.04 for the olefinic proton besides other signals due to the

methine, methoxyl and methylene protons in its ^1H nmr spectrum. An upfield chemical shift of the olefinic proton in the nmr spectrum after Dieckmann cyclization and the downward shift of the olefinic proton after dicarboxylation unequivocally established the direction of cyclization in the triesters 13 and 14.

Scheme 4 *Reagents* (a) CH_2N_2 , CHCl_3 , 4° , 7 days, 98%, (b) ethylene glycol, reflux, 30 min, 63%

Having failed to obtain the tricyclic ketone 22, by the Dieckmann cyclization of the triester 14, an alternative strategy was planned involving the preparation of the triester 25 and its conversion to the ketone 26 (Scheme 4). The ketoester 26 will be an ideal substrate for eremolactone 3 synthesis. Reaction of the triester 14 with excess diazomethane afforded the pyrazoline derivative 23 which upon pyrolysis furnished the triester 24 in good yield. The structure of 24 was deduced from its ^1H nmr spectrum which showed the presence of the protons due to the three methoxyl (δ 3.64, 3.67 and 3.73) and methyl (δ 1.99) groups besides the methine and the methylenes. The ester 24 failed to undergo 1,4-addition reaction with lithium dimethylcuprate to provide the triester 25. Several other reagents were attempted which did not produce the required dimethylated compound 25. Although the target compounds 26 and 27 could not be prepared for the synthesis of isoeremolactone, this methodology provided an easy and efficient entry to the synthesis of functionalized tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecanes.

Since the formation of the five-membered ring of the tricyclic systems 26 and 27 from the bicyclic precursor 14 could not be accomplished, an alternative strategy involving the preparation of the bicyclic dienes of the type 32 and 45 and their cycloaddition with suitable dienophiles was examined to generate the possible tricyclic precursors for eremolactone 2. A probable retrosynthetic protocol for eremolactone is indicated in the Scheme 5 wherein the tricyclic aldehyde 49 can be obtained from the diene ester 45 which is in turn made from the aromatic acid 40. In order to check the feasibility of this approach model experiments were carried out with the indane-4-carboxylic acid 29.

Scheme 5

The indane-4-carboxylic acid 29 was prepared from the known¹⁵ dicarboxylic acid 8 by cyclization¹⁸ using anhydrous aluminium chloride with NaCl to the keto acid 28 (Scheme 6), followed by Clemmensen reduction¹⁹. The structures of the products 28 and 29 were deduced from their spectral data, in particular, the ir spectrum of 28 which showed the presence of the carboxyl (1680) and ketone (1705 cm^{-1}) functional groups. Birch reduction²⁰ of the acid 29 with sodium in liquid ammonia afforded the 4,7-dihydroindane-4-carboxylic acid 30 which was treated with ethereal diazomethane to give the ester 31 in good yield. Treatment of the ester 31 with a catalytic amount of DBU in refluxing benzene furnished the conjugated diene ester 32. The structures of the dienes 31 and 32 were deduced from their spectral data and analogy with earlier¹³ observations. While the ^1H nmr spectrum of 31 showed the presence of two olefinic protons as a multiplet at δ 5.66–6.07, the conjugated diene ester 32 contained one proton appearing as a multiplet at δ 6.72. Further, the proton on the carbon bearing the ester group which appeared as a multiplet at δ 3.52–3.87 disappeared in the spectrum of 32.

Scheme 6. *Reagents* . (a) $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHCO}_2\text{Et}$, PhH , 80° , 72%, (b) 10% $\text{KOH}-\text{MeOH}$, Δ , 96%, (c) $\text{Ni}-\text{Al}$, NaOH , 83%, (d) for $\text{R}=\text{H}$: NaCl , AlCl_3 , 160° , 65%, for $\text{R}=\text{Me}$: PPA , 76%, (e) $\text{Zn}-\text{Hg}$, HCl , MeOH

Cycloaddition of the diene ester **32** with 2-chloroacrylonitrile afforded regioselectively¹³ the adduct **33** (Scheme 7) which showed ir absorptions at 1700 and 2225 cm^{-1} (unsaturated ester and nitrile functional groups). Hydrolysis of the adduct **33** with aqueous KOH in DMSO at 55° for 48 h gave the keto acid which was esterified with ethereal diazomethane to the tricyclic methyl ester **34** which showed the ir absorptions at 1720 and 1705 cm^{-1} . The ^1H nmr spectrum of **34** showed resonances at δ 3.6 as a multiplet for the bridgehead proton, a triplet at 2.76 for the allylic methylene and a doublet at 2.07 for the methylene protons adjacent to the keto group. The mass spectrum of this tricyclic ester **34** showed a base peak at m/z 178 corresponding to the diene **32** due to the retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation. Treatment of the keto ester **34** with sodium hydride and excess of methyl iodide in 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME) afforded the *gem*-dimethylated derivative **36**. The ^1H nmr spectrum of **36** showed the presence of protons due to the methoxyl at δ 3.77 as a singlet, methylenes as two singlets at 0.96 and 1.1, the bridgehead proton as a multiplet at 3.52 besides the methylene protons, confirming the structure assigned to it.

Scheme 7 Reagents (a) Na liq NH₃, THF, (b) CH₂N₂, ether, (c) DBU, PhI, Δ , (d) CH₂=C(Cl)CN, PhI, 85°, (e) KOH, DMSO, CH₂N₂, ether, (f) NaH, MeI, DME

Having successfully accomplished the construction of the tricyclic framework present in eremolactone in the model system, the synthesis of the tricyclic ketone **48**, required for the eremolactone synthesis was undertaken along the above lines. Thus 1-methylindane-7-carboxylic acid **42** was prepared from 2-acetylbenzoic acid²¹ **37** (Scheme 6). Reaction of **37** with ethyl triphenylphosphoranylideneacetate afforded the lactone **38** whose ir spectrum showed bands at 1780 cm^{-1}

due to the lactone and 1740 cm^{-1} due to the ester group. The ^1H nmr spectrum of **37** showed a quartet at δ 3.93 (J 7 Hz), a triplet at 1.1 (J 7 Hz) due to the ethyl group, a singlet at 2.9 due to the methylene protons adjacent to the ester group and a singlet at 1.73 for the methyl group besides the four aromatic protons appearing as a multiplet at 7.2–7.9. The lactone **38**, upon treatment with ethanolic KOH furnished the unsaturated diacid **39**, as a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers, evidenced from its spectral data. The ^1H nmr spectrum of **39** showed the presence of methyl resonances at δ 2.1 and 2.36 (J 2 Hz) in the ratio of 2 : 5 and the vinylic proton at 5.6 and 5.73 (J 2 Hz) in the ratio of 5 : 2 indicating that the *E*-isomer is present to an extent of 72%. This mixture of unsaturated acids **39** was reduced¹⁵ with Ni-Al alloy to the diacid **40**. Cyclization of the acid **40** with polyphosphoric acid (PPA) afforded the ketoacid **41** in good yield. Clemmensen reduction of the ketoacid **41** gave 1-methylindane-7-carboxylic acid **42** in good yield.

Birch reduction of **42** afforded the dihydroacid **43** (Scheme 7) which gave the unconjugated ester **44** with ethereal diazomethane. Refluxing the ester **44** with DBU in benzene gave the conjugated compound **45** which smoothly underwent cycloaddition with 2-chloroacrylonitrile resulting in the adduct **46**. Hydrolysis of the adduct **46** with KOH in DMSO yielded the ketoacid which on esterification with ethereal diazomethane afforded the ketoester **47**. The ir spectrum of **47** showed the presence of an unsaturated ester (1720) and the ketone (1700 cm^{-1}) functionality, while the ^1H nmr spectrum of **47** showed the presence of the methyl group as a doublet at δ 1.06 (J 7 Hz), a methoxyl group as a singlet at 3.7, the bridgehead proton as a multiplet at 3.6 besides other signals due to the methine and methylene protons. Treatment of the ketoester **47** with excess of methyl iodide in the presence of sodium hydride gave the *gem*-dimethylated derivative **48**. The ^1H nmr spectrum of **48** showed the presence of two singlets at δ 0.96 and 1.11 for the *gem*-dimethyl groups, a doublet at 1.05 for the methyl group present in the five-membered ring, a singlet at 3.77 for the carbomethoxyl group besides other methine and methylene protons which conclusively proved its structure. Compound **48** had all the structural features present in eremolactone. It is interesting to note that the conversion of the conjugated diene ester **45** into the adducts **46** and **47** unexpectedly produced a single product despite a stereogenic centre in the five-membered ring which should result in an epimeric mixture (methyl-*endo* and -*exo*). Compounds **46**, **47** and **48** showed only a single doublet for the methyl group in their ^1H nmr spectra.

Having successfully completed the preparation of the tricyclic ketone **48**, the next step in the synthesis of eremolactone is to convert the ketone **48** into the aldehyde **50** through a one-carbon homologation. Reaction of **48** with

methoxymethylenetriphenylphosphorane followed by hydrolysis failed to produce any of the desired compound. The starting material was recovered unchanged. Other reagents such as excess of methylenetriphenylphosphorane, methyl lithium, methyl magnesium iodide and lithium acetylide did not react with the ketoester **48** indicating that the keto group is extremely unreactive towards conventional reagents. Similarly, compound **36** could not be converted into the aldehyde **49**. Although the synthesis of eremolactone and isoeremolactone could not be accomplished, we have developed a new strategy for the construction of functionalized tricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undecanes from readily available aromatic precursors. Further work towards eremolactone is in progress.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected and were recorded on a Mettler FP1 instrument. Ir spectra (liquid films, solution in chloroform or nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃, unless otherwise stated) on a JEOL FX-90Q spectrometer with SiMe₄ as internal standard, and mass spectra on a JEOL MS-DX 303 instrument with a built-in direct inlet system. Microanalyses were carried out using a Carlo Erba 1106 analyzer. All anhydrous solvents were prepared by standard procedures. Analytical tlc was performed on glass plates coated with Acme's silica gel G (containing 13% calcium sulphate as the binder), and Acme's silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used for column chromatography. All reactions involving air and moisture sensitive reagents were performed under a blanket of argon filled in balloons. Hexane refers to petroleum ether fraction of boiling range 60–80°.

2-Carboxyethylcyclohexa-2,5-diene-1-carboxylic acid 9 and methyl 2-carbomethoxyethylcyclohexa-2,5-diene-1-carboxylate 10 : Sodium metal (4.6 g, 0.2 mol) was added in portions to a stirred solution of 3-(2-carboxyphenyl)propanoic acid¹⁵ **8** (9.7 g, 50 mmol), dry THF (30 ml) and anhydrous liquid ammonia (500 ml). The resulting blue coloured solution was stirred for 1 h, the excess sodium destroyed by adding solid ammonium chloride till the reaction mixture became colourless and ammonia was allowed to evaporate. The resulting slurry was dissolved in water, acidified with 5% HCl, and extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic extracts were washed with water, brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent yielded the dihydro acid **9** as a crystalline solid in quantitative yield, m.p. 126–28° (hexane) (Found : C, 61.31; H, 6.2. C₁₀H₁₂O₄ requires : C, 61.22; H, 6.16%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3300–2600, 1712, 1655 and 980 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 2.4 (4H, br s, CH₂CH₂COOH), 2.56–2.83 (2H, m, doubly allylic), 3.4–3.76 (1H, m, CHCOOH), 5.62–5.76 (3H, m, olefinic) and 10.3 (2H, br, COOH).

The above diacid **9** (4.6 g) was treated with ethereal diazomethane. Excess diazomethane was then removed by

bubbling nitrogen. Ether was removed to give the diester **10** as a colourless liquid (quant), ν_{\max} (neat) 1735, 1625 and 1435 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 2.3 (4H, br s, CH₂CH₂CO₂H), 2.6–2.82 (2H, m, doubly allylic), 3.1 (1H, br s, CHCOOMe), 3.59 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.66 (3H, s, COOMe) and 5.4–5.78 (3H, m, olefinic) (Found : M⁺, 224.1036. C₁₂H₁₆O₄ requires : M, 224.1049).

1-Carboxyethylcyclohexa-1,3-diene-2-carboxylic acid 11 : 2-Carboxyethylcyclohexa-2,5-diene-1-carboxylic acid 9 (4.9 g, 25 mmol) was refluxed with 20% aq. NaOH solution (25 ml) for 6 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ethyl acetate. The combined organic extracts were washed with little water, brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed to afford the conjugated diene **11** as a highly viscous material (4.31 g, 88%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3500–2570, 1690, 1670, 1600 and 1280 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.8–3.1 (8H, br m), 5.71 (1H, br d, C3-olefinic H) and 6.28 (1H, m, C4-olefinic H) (Found : M⁺, 196.0729. C₁₀H₁₂C₄ requires : M, 196.0735).

Methyl 1-carbomethoxyethylcyclohexa-1,3-diene-2-carboxylate 12 : The diester **10** (4.5 g, 20 mmol) was refluxed with DBU (0.5 ml) in benzene (50 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was washed with 2% HCl, water, brine and dried. The solvent was evaporated to give the conjugated diester **12** as a light yellow liquid (4.3 g, 97%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1735, 1720 and 1595 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.85–3.0 (8H, br m), 3.52 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.6 (3H, s, COOMe), 5.68 (1H, br d, C3-olefinic H) and 6.23 (1H, m, C4-olefinic H) (Found: M⁺, 224.1039. C₁₂H₁₆O₄ requires : M, 224.1049).

Dimethyl endo-1-carbomethoxyethylbicyclo[2.2.2]oct-2-ene-2,5-dicarboxylate 13 and dimethyl endo-1-carbomethoxyethylbicyclo[2.2.2]oct-2-ene-2,6-dicarboxylate 14 : A degassed benzene solution of the conjugated diene **11** (2.96 g, 15 mmol), methyl acrylate (5.4 ml, 60 mmol) and hydroquinone (10 mg) was heated in a sealed tube at 110° for 32 h. After cooling, the solvent was removed and the crude product was esterified with ethereal diazomethane. Removal of the solvent and chromatography of the crude product over silica gel [ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 8) as eluent] initially afforded **13**. Further elution gave the triester **14**. The two regioisomers **13** and **14** were obtained as highly viscous oils in a 1 : 2 ratio (2.43 g, 52%).

The conjugated diester **12** (3.36 g, 15 mmol) and methyl acrylate (2.7 ml, 30 mmol) were taken in benzene (20 ml) and refluxed for 30 h. Benzene was removed and the crude product was chromatographed to give the same ratio of the adducts **13** and **14** (3.39 g, 73%) : **14** (Found : C, 62.12; H, 7.17. C₁₆H₂₂O₆ requires : C, 61.92; H, 7.15%), ν_{\max} (neat) 2952, 1740, 1716 and 1608 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.1–2.42 (10H, m, 5 × CH₂), 2.53 (1H, dd, *J* 10 and 6 Hz, CHCOOMe), 2.63–2.8 (1H, m, bridgehead proton), 3.53 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.56 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.6 (3H, s, COOMe) and 7.2 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, olefinic H) (Found : M⁺, 310.1409. C₁₆H₂₂O₆ requires : M, 310.1416);

13 (Found : C, 62.08; H, 7.18. $C_{16}H_{22}O_6$ requires : C, 61.92; H, 7.15%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1740, 1715 and 1610 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.16–2.53 (10H, m, $5 \times \text{CH}_2$), 2.56–2.66 (1H, m, CHCOOMe), 2.8–3.1 (1H, m, bridgehead proton), 3.5 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.54 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.62 (3H, s, COOMe) and 7.02 (1H, d, 7.1 Hz, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 310.1411. $C_{16}H_{22}O_6$ requires : M, 310.1416).

Dimethyl cis-1-carbomethoxyethylbicyclo[2.2.2]octane-2,6-dicarboxylate 16 : A mixture of the adduct **14** (0.31 g, 1 mmol) and 10% Pd-charcoal (50 mg) was stirred in methanol in an atmosphere of hydrogen until the hydrogen absorption ceased. The catalyst was filtered off and methanol was removed. Purification of the product by column chromatography over silica gel using ethyl acetate and hexane (1 : 10) as eluent afforded the triester **16** as a colourless liquid (quant), ν_{\max} (neat) 2950, 1730 and 1198 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 1.25–2.95 (15H, m) and 3.65 and 3.67 (9H, 2s, $3 \times \text{COOMe}$), δ_{C} (22.5 MHz) 23.57, 24.93, 26.59, 29.03, 31.66, 32.93, 36.34, 43.36, 51.36, 51.55, 174.42 and 174.81 (Found : M^+ , 312.1569. $C_{16}H_{24}O_6$ requires : M, 312.1573).

Dimethyl cis-1-carbomethoxyethylbicyclo[2.2.2]octane-2,5-dicarboxylate 15 : Hydrogenation of the isomeric adduct **13** (1 mmol) using 10% Pd-charcoal as described above furnished the saturated triester **15** upon column chromatography as a colourless liquid in quantitative yield, ν_{\max} (neat) 1732 and 1165 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.25–2.9 (15H, m), 3.66 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{COOMe}$) and 3.71 (3H, s, COOMe), δ_{C} (22.5 MHz) 25.52, 25.73, 26.71, 28.76, 28.98, 32.87, 33.3, 37.11, 41.75, 42.75, 44.59, 51.52, 51.74, 173.41, 174.39 and 174.47 (Found : M^+ , 312.1576. $C_{16}H_{24}O_6$ requires : M, 312.1573).

Dimethyl 4-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-3,9-dicarboxylate 19 : A solution of the triester **14** (281 mg, 0.9 mmol) in benzene (5 ml) was added to a stirred suspension of sodium hydride (36 mg, 60% dispersion, 0.9 mmol) in benzene (15 ml). A few drops of methanol were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed in for 6 h. The solution was cooled, poured into cold 2% aq. sulfuric acid and extracted with ether. Combined ethereal layers was washed with water, brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). The crude product, thus obtained, was purified by chromatography [silica gel, ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 5)] to give the β -ketoester **19** as a gummy liquid (178 mg, 71%), ν_{\max} (neat) 2980, 1735, 1650 and 1595 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 0.81–2.5 (9H, m), 2.56 (1H, dd, J 10 and 5 Hz, CHCOOMe), 2.87–3.24 (1H, m, bridgehead proton), 3.66 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.77 (3H, s, COOMe) and 6.64 (1H, d, 7.1 Hz, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 178.1156. $C_{15}H_{18}O_5$ requires : M, 278.1154).

Dimethyl 4-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-3,8-dicarboxylate 17 : Dieckmann cyclization of the triester **13** (0.8 mmol) using sodium hydride (32 mg, 0.8 mmol) in benzene (15 ml) as described above afforded, after purification using column chromatography, the β -ketoester **17** as a thick liquid (151 mg, 68%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1738, 1654 and 1590 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 0.8–2.76 (10H, m), 2.84–3.09 (1H, m, bridgehead proton), 3.62 (3H,

s, COOMe), 3.74 (3H, s, COOMe) and 6.56 (1H, d, 7.1 Hz, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 278.1157. $C_{15}H_{18}O_5$ requires : M, 278.1154).

Methyl 4-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-9-carboxylate 20 : A mixture of the β -ketoester **19** (45 mg, 0.16 mmol), sodium chloride (2 mg, 0.034 mmol), DMSO (5 ml) and water (10 ml) was heated at 110° under nitrogen atmosphere for 16 h. It was then cooled, extracted with ether and the combined ether extracts was washed with water, brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent followed by column chromatography over silica gel using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 9) as eluent afforded the ketoester **20** as a colourless liquid (26 mg, 72%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1734, 1716 and 1610 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} (270 MHz) 1.13–2.18 (8H, m, methylene protons), 2.44 (2H, t, CH_2CO), 2.78 (1H, dd, J 10.2 and 6 Hz, CHCOOMe), 3 (1H, m, bridgehead H), 3.6 (3H, s, COOMe) and 7.18 (1H, d, J 6.6, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 220.1101. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3$ requires : M, 220.1099).

Methyl 4-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-8-carboxylate 18 : Decarboxylation of the β -ketoester **17** (45 mg, 0.16 mmol) using sodium chloride (2 mg) and DMSO (5 ml) as described above furnished the ketoester **18** as colourless oil (28 mg, 74%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1735 and 1715 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} (270 MHz) 1.21–2.04 (8H, m, methylene protons), 2.45–2.51 (2H, m, CH_2CO), 2.76–2.88 (1H, m, bridgehead H), 3.62 (3H, s, COOMe) and 7.04 (1H, d, 7.1 Hz, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 220.1111. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3$ requires : M, 220.1099).

Dimethyl endo-1-carbomethoxyethyl-3-methylbicyclo[2.2.2]oct-2-ene-2,6-dicarboxylate 24 : The triester **14** (3.1 g, 10 mmol) in chloroform (20 ml) was treated with a large excess of ethereal diazomethane in a stoppered flask and protected from light, and left at 4° for 10 days. When the reaction was complete (monitored by tlc), the excess diazomethane was removed by flushing Ar into the reaction mixture. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure followed by recrystallization from ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the pyrazoline derivative **23** as colourless crystals (3.45 g, 98%), m.p. $110\text{--}12^\circ$ (ethyl acetate-hexane), ν_{\max} (nujol) 2945 and 1735 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} (270 MHz) 0.85–2.94 (13H, complex multiplet), 3.63 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.7 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{COOMe}$), 4.62 (1H, dd, J 18.4 and 8.3 Hz, =NCH) and 4.77 (1H, dd, J 18.4 and 2.35 Hz, =NCH).

The above pyrazoline derivative **23** (1.76 mg, 5 mmol) was refluxed in ethylene glycol (50 ml) for 30 min. After cooling, water was added and extracted with ether. Combined ether layers was washed with water, brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent followed by purification by column chromatography [silica gel, ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 6)] afforded the triester **24** as a colourless oil (1.02 g, 63%), (Found : C, 62.72; H, 7.44. $C_{17}H_{24}O_6$ requires : C, 62.95, H, 7.46%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1735, 1715, 1435 and 1265 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} (270 MHz) 1.25–2.42 (8H, m, $4 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.99 (3H, s, =CMe),

2.48 (2H, m, CH₂COOMe), 2.58 (1H, dd, *J* 9.6 and 5.3 Hz, CHCOOMe), 2.7–2.8 (1H, m, bridgehead H), 3.64 (3H, s, COOMe), 3.67 (3H, s, COOMe) and 3.73 (3H, s, COOMe).

1-Oxindane-4-carboxylic acid 28 : A mixture of the diacid¹⁵ **8** (8.6 g, 44 mmol), pulverised anhyd. AlCl₃ (30 g) and NaCl (2.7 g) was heated for 2 h at 160° with occasional stirring. After cooling, the complex was decomposed with conc. HCl (30 ml) in ice (40 g). The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallized from acetone-benzene to afford colourless needles of **28** (5.12 g, 65.6%), m.p. 226° (lit.¹⁸ 225.5–27.5°) (acetone-benzene) (Found : C, 68.31; H, 4.69. C₁₀H₈O₃ requires : C, 68.18; H, 4.58%), ν_{\max} (nujol) 3300–3100, 1705, 1680, 1570 and 1420 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 2.66 (2H, m, CH₂CO), 3.48 (2H, m, ArCH₂), 7.54 (2H, dd, *J* 7.2 Hz, ArH₆), 7.86 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, ArH₇) and 8.26 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, ArH₅).

Indane-4-carboxylic acid 29 : A mixture of amalgamated zinc (prepared from 13 g zinc dust, 1 g HgCl₂), conc. HCl (15 ml), water (10 ml) and the keto acid **28** (4.34 g, 24.7 mmol) taken in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The combined organic extracts were washed with water, brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent gave a crude product which was crystallized from ethyl acetate to afford **29** (3.91 g, 83%), m.p. 136° (ethyl acetate) (Found : C, 74.18; H, 6.28. C₁₀H₁₀O₂ requires : C, 74.06; H, 6.21%), ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 1685 and 1595 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} (acetone-d₆) 2.16 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.03 (2H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz, ArC¹H₂), 3.37 (2H, t, *J* 7.7, ArC³H₂) and 7.28–7.97 (3H, m, ArH).

4,7-Dihydroindane-4-carboxylic acid 30 and methyl 4,7-dihydroindane-4-carboxylate 31 : Sodium metal (0.9 g) was added in portions to a stirred solution of the acid **29** (2 g, 12.3 mmol) in dry THF (15 ml) and anhydrous liquid ammonia (125 ml). The resulting blue coloured solution was stirred for 1 h, excess sodium destroyed by adding solid ammonium chloride till the reaction mixture became colourless and ammonia was allowed to evaporate. The resulting slurry was dissolved in water and washed with ether to remove organic impurities. It was then acidified with 5% HCl and extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic extracts were washed with water, brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent yielded the dihydro acid **30** which was recrystallized from hexane (1.95 g, 96%), m.p. 54.8° (hexane) (Found : C, 73.21; H, 7.44. C₁₀H₁₂O₂ requires : C, 73.15; H, 7.37%), ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 1695, 1400 and 920 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.73–2.08 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.2–2.5 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 2.57–2.78 (2H, m, =CCH₂C=), 3.67–3.94 (1H, m, CHCOOH) and 5.70–6.11 (2H, m, olefinic H); δ_{C} (22.5 MHz) 21.27(t), 27.24(t), 33.98(t), 35.19(t), 44.15(d), 121.87(d), 127.07(d), 128.06(s), 135.25(s) and 178.81(s).

The above dihydro acid **30** (1.9 g, 11.6 mmol) in ether (25 ml) was treated with ethereal diazomethane. After 4 h, the solvent was removed to give a quantitative yield of the

dihydroindane ester **31** as colourless liquid, ν_{\max} (neat) 3025 and 1735 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.72–2.2 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.16–2.53 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 2.57–2.86 (2H, m, =CCH₂C=), 3.52–3.87 (1H, m, CHCOOMe), 3.7 (3H, s, COOMe) and 5.66–6.07 (2H, m, olefinic H) (Found : M⁺, 178.0996. C₁₁H₁₄O₂ requires : M, 178.0994).

Methyl 6,7-dihydroindane-4-carboxylate 32 : The unconjugated ester **31** (1.9 g, 10.8 mmol) was refluxed with DBU (0.3 ml) in benzene (30 ml) for 6 h. The benzene layer was washed successively with 2% HCl, water, brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent gave a colourless liquid **32** (1.89 g, quant), ν_{\max} (neat) 1722 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 0.98–2.8 (10H, m, CH₂), 3.67 (3H, s, OMe) and 6.72 (1H, m, olefinic H) (Found : M⁺, 178.0997. C₁₁H₁₄O₂ requires : M, 178.0994).

Methyl 9-chloro-9-cyanotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-6-carboxylate 33 : A solution of the conjugated diene ester **32** (1.85 g, 11.28 mmol), 2-chloroacrylonitrile (3 ml) and hydroquinone (20 mg) was refluxed in benzene for 40 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was recrystallized from hexane to afford colourless needles of the adduct **33** (2.2 g, 79.7%) as an epimeric mixture at C-9, m.p. 93.2° (hexane) (Found : C, 63.31; H, 6.16; N, 5.16. C₁₄H₁₆O₂NCl requires : C, 63.28; H, 6.07; N, 5.27%), ν_{\max} (nujol) 2225, 1700 and 1080 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} 1.29–3 (12H, m, CH₂), 3.34 (1H, m, bridgehead H) and 3.78 (3H, s, OMe).

Methyl 9-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-6-carboxylate 34 : A solution of the adduct **33** (1.87 g, 7.04 mmol) in DMSO (30 ml) and 20% aqueous KOH (10 ml) was stirred at 55° for 48 h. The reaction mixture was acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts were washed with water, brine and dried over (Na₂SO₄). The crude acid obtained after removal of the solvent was esterified with ethereal diazomethane and purified by chromatography over silica gel. Elution with ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 19) afforded the ketoester **34** as a colourless liquid (0.902 g, 58%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1720, 1705 and 1650 cm⁻¹, δ_{H} (200 MHz) 1.40–1.89 (7H, m), 2.07 (2H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₂CO), 2.5 (1H, m), 2.76 (2H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, =CCH₂), 3.6 (1H, m, bridgehead) and 3.77 (3H, s, OMe), δ_{C} (22.5 MHz) 24.94(t), 25.59(t), 27.41(2t), 31.06(t), 32.1(d), 39.12(t), 50.17(q), 61.1(s), 127.43(s), 160.33(s), 163.84(s) and 208.45(s), *m/z* 220(M⁺, 71%), 178(100), 161(28), 145(68), 119(76) (Found : M⁺, 220.1101. C₁₃H₁₆O₃ requires : M, 220.1099).

Methyl 8,8-dimethyl-9-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-6-carboxylate 36 : The ketone **34** (0.8 g, 3.64 mmol) in DME (15 ml) was added slowly to a stirred suspension of NaH (0.435 g, 10.9 mmol) in DME (25 ml) under a balloon of Ar. After stirring for 20 min at room temperature the solution was cooled to 0°, and MeI (4 ml) was introduced and stirred for another 30 min. After heating the reaction mixture at 60° for 4 h, an additional amount of MeI (2 ml) was added and stirred for 2 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with dil. HCl and extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts was

washed with water, aqueous sodium thiosulphate and brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was evaporated and the residue was purified by chromatography on silica gel and elution with ethyl acetate and hexane (1 : 19) afforded the ketoester **36** as colourless oil (0.79 g, 89%) (Found : C, 72.37; H, 7.98. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 72.55; H, 8.12%), ν_{max} (neat) 1710, 1700 and 1645 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 0.96 (3H, s, Me), 1.1 (3H, s, Me), 1.03–2.1 (7H, m, CH_2), 2.52 (1H, m), 2.74 (2H, m, allylic CH_2), 3.52 (1H, m, bridgehead H) and 3.77 (3H, s, COOMe).

The lactone 38 : A solution of 2-acetylbenzoic acid **37** (16.4 g, 0.1 mol) and ethyl triphenylphosphoranylidene acetate (38.3 g, 0.11 mol) in dry benzene (300 ml) was refluxed for 12 h under nitrogen atmosphere. After removal of the solvent, the crude product was chromatographed over silica gel using ethyl acetate-hexane (1 : 3) to afford the lactone **38** as a gummy liquid (16.8 g, 72%), ν_{max} (neat) 1780, 1740 and 1600 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.1 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.73 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.9 (2H, s, CHCOO), 3.93 (2H, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3) and 7.2–7.9 (4H, m, ArH) (Found : M^+ , 234.0876. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires : M, 234.0892).

3-(2-Carboxyphenyl)but-2-enoic acid (cis : trans, 1 : 2.5) **39** : The lactone **38** (11.7 g, 50 mmol) was refluxed in 10% ethanolic KOH (110 ml) for 6 h. After removal of ethanol, the residue was dissolved in water (200 ml) and acidified with dil. HCl. The product **39** was obtained as a light yellow solid (9.9 g, 96%), m.p. 111–23° (CH_2Cl_2) (Found : C, 64.18; H, 4.92. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 64.08; H, 4.89%), ν_{max} (nujol) 3400–2300, 1690, 1630 and 1595 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 2.1 and 2.36 (3H, 2d, J 2 Hz, CH_3), 5.6 and 5.73 (1H, 2q, J 2 Hz, =CH), 6.73–8 (4H, m, ArH) and 10.5 (2H, br s, COOH) (Found : M^+ , 206.0576. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires : M, 206.0579).

3-(2-Carboxyphenyl)butanoic acid 40 : Ni–Al (1 : 1) alloy (27 g) was added in portions to a mechanically stirred solution of **39** (10.3 g, 50 mmol) in 10% aq. NaOH (275 ml) over a period of 90 min with external water cooling. The solution was heated to 90° and stirred for 1 h. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and washed with 10% NaOH solution (25 ml) and hot water (50 ml). The combined filtrates was added dropwise in conc. HCl (170 ml). The solid, thus obtained, was filtered off to give the diacid **40** (8.63 g, 83%), m.p. 144–46° (hot water), ν_{max} (nujol) 3200–2500, 1705 and 1680 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 1.3 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH_3), 2.4–2.6 (2H, m, CH_2), 3.8–4.46 (1H, m, CH), 7.0–7.86 (4H, m, ArH) and 9.63 (2H, br s, COOH) (Found : M^+ , 208.0717. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires : M, 208.0735).

3-Methyl-1-oxoindane-4-carboxylic acid 41 : The diacid **40** (5.2 g, 25 mmol) was stirred with polyphosphoric acid (prepared from 110 g phosphorous pentoxide and 55 ml orthophosphoric acid) at 100° for 30 min. The resulting clear brown solution was cooled, poured into ice-water and extracted with dichloromethane. After the usual workup, the ketoacid **41** was obtained as a crystalline solid (3.61 g, 76%),

m.p. 185° (hot water) (Found : C, 69.72; H, 5.41. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 69.47; H, 5.3%), ν_{max} (nujol) 3200–2500, 1715, 1695 and 1585 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.36 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 2.26 (1H, dd, J 19 and 2 Hz, CH_2), 2.93 (1H, dd, J 19 and 7 Hz, CH_2), 3.83–4.43 (1H, m, CH), 7.5 (1H, d, J 7.3 Hz, ArH₆), 7.83 (1H, dd, J 7.3 and 2 Hz, ArH₇), 8.23 (1H, dd, J 7.3 and 2 Hz, ArH₅) and 9.13 (1H, br peak, COOH) (Found : M^+ , 190.0633. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires : M, 190.0630).

1-Methylindan-7-carboxylic acid 42 : Using the procedure described for the preparation of **29**, the keto-acid **41** (4.75 g) was reduced to give **42** (3.7 g, 84%) as a solid, m.p. 105–106° (CH_2Cl_2), ν_{max} (nujol) 3300–2500, 1690 and 1590 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.0 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.43–3.2 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 3.63–4.2 (1H, m, CH), 6.93–7.46 (2H, m, ArH), 7.8 (1H, dd, J 7.2 and 2 Hz, ArH₆) and 10.1 (1H, br s, COOH) (Found : M^+ , 176.0838. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires : M, 176.0837).

Methyl 1-methyl-4,7-dihydroindan-7-carboxylate 44 : Birch reduction of **42** (2 g) using sodium (1 g) as described for the preparation of **31** followed by the treatment with diazomethane, yielded the dihydro ester **44** as a clear oil (2.14 g, quant), ν_{max} (neat) 3100, 1740 and 1435 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.0 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 0.83–2.45 (5H, m, CHCH_2CH), 2.47–2.93 (2H, m, doubly allylic CH_2), 3.43–3.83 (1H, m, CHCOOMe), 3.56 (3H, s, COOCH_3) and 5.4–6 (2H, m, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 192.1152. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires : M, 192.1151).

Methyl 1-methyl-4,5-dihydroindane-7-carboxylate 45 : Compound **44** (0.8 g) was refluxed with DBU (5 drops) in benzene for 6 h. Workup as described for **32** afforded **45** (0.8 g, quant) as an oily compound, ν_{max} (neat) 1720 and 1435 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 0.96 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 0.97–2.8 (9H, m, methylene and methine protons), 3.67 (3H, s, COOCH_3) and 6.83–6.56 (1H, m, olefinic H) (Found : M^+ , 192.1156. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires : M, 192.1151).

Methyl 9-chloro-9-cyano-4-methyltricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-6-carboxylate 46 : Diels-Alder reaction of **45** (0.4 g) with 2-chloroacrylonitrile (1 ml), as described for **33**, gave a crude product which was chromatographed over silica gel using ethyl acetate-hexane (1.19) as eluent to furnish the tricyclic compound **46** (0.36 g, 62%) as a colourless solid (Found : C, 64.36; H, 6.52; N, 5.06. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{ClN}$ requires : C, 64.4; H, 6.48; N, 5.01%), ν_{max} (neat) 2230, 1705 and 1620 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 0.83–2.73 (11H, m, methylene and methine protons), 1.13 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 3.13–3.43 (1H, m, bridgehead H) and 3.73 (3H, s, COOCH_3) (Found : M^+ , 270.1023. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{ClN}$ requires : M, 279.1026).

Methyl 4-methyl-9-oxotricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-6-carboxylate 47 : Hydrolysis of the chlorocyano compound **46** (200 mg) using dimethyl sulfoxide (2 ml) and 20% aq. KOH (1 g) as described above for **34** followed by esterification with ethereal diazomethane and purification by column chromatography [silica gel, ethyl acetate-hexane (1.20)] furnished the ketoester **47** as colourless oil (141 mg, 84%),

ν_{\max} (neat) 1720, 1700 and 1640 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 1.06 (3H, d, 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.2–2.03 (9H, m, methylene protons), 2.37–2.7 (1H, m), 3.0–3.6 (2H, m, bridgehead H and allylic H) and 3.7 (3H, s, COOCH_3), m/z 234 (M^+ , 62%), 192(100), 175(32) and 133(66) (Found : M^+ , 234.1252. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires : M, 234.1256).

Methyl 9-oxo-4,8,8-trimethyltricyclo[5.2.2.0^{1,5}]undec-5-ene-6-carboxylate 48 : Using the procedure described for the methylation of 36, the keto-ester 47 (100 mg) was methylated (100 mg, sodium hydride, 2 ml methyl iodide and 10 ml DME) and chromatographed (silica gel : ethyl acetate-hexane, 1 : 20) to give the tricyclic compound 48 as a colourless liquid (85 mg, 76%), ν_{\max} (neat) 1710, 1700 and 1645 cm^{-1} , δ_{H} 0.96 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.05 (3H, d, 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.11 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.03–2.1 (7H, m, CH_2), 2.4–2.6 (1H, m), 3.15–3.35 (2H, m, bridgehead proton and allylic proton) and 3.77 (3H, s, COOCH_3) (Found : M^+ , 262.1578. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires : M, 262.1569).

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